

光子结构和特性

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摘要：基于已有实验事实，提出一个适用于单个光子的光子圆柱形结构模型。并给出基于单光子圆柱形结构模型的光子特性。光是波长很短的电磁波，又是由光子组成的，这已为实验所证实。因此，单个光子就是一列电磁波。研究新发现，每个光子都应是单色的，单个光子可能具有圆柱形结构，光子可能与基能有关联。基能意思是基本能量。提出物质是基能的有序运动，基能的无序运动使其仍处于基能状态的观点。有序性是其关键。真空中的光子或电磁波是基能的有序运动，是有限有界的能量场。如果光子中的能量无序的运动，它就会变回基能。光子中电磁场的分布和存在，不是任何已知物质的空间分布，是基能存在的强力证据。单光子圆柱形结构模型的研究结果表明，如何做到正确的理解和确定光子体积大小、光子横向尺度、光子传播方向长度、光子周期数，以及机械地把一个光子切成两个和弯曲一个光子的可能性。这些都可以通过提出的实验验证。另外，建议的光子实验及其测量结果，将会证实上述理论和预言、光子界面及其存在性、光子电磁场与基能间的可能联系。

关键词：光子结构，光子横向尺度，光子传播方向长度，光子周期数，基能

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光是波长很短的电磁波并由光子组成，这已为实验证实。因此单个光子就是一列电磁波。光子研究中可以深入考虑的挑战有很多。例如，一个光子，其形状、体积和结构是什么样的？有无明确的边界？永恒的无损耗的电磁场转换过程及如何转换？

基于下述对光子的物理分析，这里作者提出一个光子结构模型，见图1。

光子有界。按照物质传播速度有限，即小于等于光速，的原理，从光子发射和吸收的过程，可以推论出，光子是有界的。因为如果其分布是无限的，在有限的吸收或发射时间内，用有限速度，不可能从无限的空间分布中返回。

光子完整性。光子的有界性，即有明确的光子界面，可保证其完整性。意即在光子吸收的过程中，是整个光子完全被吸收，而没有光子的任何部分残留下来。这已被实验证实且符合量子力学要求和处理过程。光子完整性的特征使得光子是稳定的且不衰变。观测到的从数光年外的恒星发出的光表明光子在宇宙空间中传播是稳定的且不衰变。

这会导致现实中电子的电场分布是有界的并有一个明确界面的结论。进而带电粒子与其界面附近的基能之间，会存在能量交换过程。基能意思是基本能量。

光子吸收和发射过程。原子吸收和发射可见光，即可见的光子。原子核吸收和放射不同波长的 γ 射线，即 γ 光子。这种过程是一种现存能量状态之间的转换，

例如光子和原子中的电子质子能量场。这是电子-质子能场间转换的一种形式。因此下列假设是合理的：因为物质存在方式应该是对应相关的，协调相容的，光子尺度应与其发射吸收主体的尺度大小相当且密切相关。由此可以选取氢原子尺度作为可见光比较或测量的参考标准。

光子单色性。 单个光子只是单色的，具有确定的频率。由于多普勒效应，相同原子能级发出光子的频率可能是不同的，但是每个光子是单色的并且已被光谱分析实验证实。基于这些概念，太阳光谱，由于是由光子一个接一个形成的，虽然在物理上认为是连续的，但是在数学上应该是不连续的，是由点组成的，所以在两个相邻光子之间将会有极其微小的间隔。

光子尺度。 可见光子的吸收和发射与原子有关而 γ 光子与原子核有关。原子和原子核的尺度是不同的，所以可见和 γ 光子的尺度也是不同的。基于上述事实 and 氢原子能谱作为参考标准，作者为可见光子提出光子尺度公式， $L_0 = \alpha \nu_H / \nu$ ，其中 α 是光子长度因子，其值约为1，单位 \AA ， ν_H 是氢原子光谱频率， ν 是可见光子频率。提出的光子空间形状为近似圆柱形，长轴方向为其传播方向，见图1，这可用实验测量和证实，见图2和实验1和2。

光子结构。 直观物理判断形成的主要概念性结论表明，可以假设光子结构及其空间分布的形状是一个圆柱体或准圆柱体，见图1。在光子体积内及其分界面的空间能量或物质分布是有限和封闭的电磁波。像平面电磁波一样，其动态电磁场在相位上是垂直的。圆柱体的轴线方向是它的传播方向。在光子内，其空间分布是基能有序运动的一种模式。有序的基能构成光子是一个合理的假设。

光反射作用过程和光子弯曲。 学术界普遍的观点，不认为光子是点粒子，即不占有空间体积也没有其大小和长度。当有限长度的光子反射时，这时已不是直线传播。在反射点，光子的传播过程是像粒子那样通过碰撞或像波作用过程那样，其轨迹或传播线是圆弧形或折线式？关键是光子与反射物体的相对大小，二者的尺度大小相当才适合反射。例如可见光的光子是被原子通过碰撞反射的。在适当的条件下，一个光子也可能被弯曲，见可能的光子弯曲实验3。

场概念。 场，例如电子电场或原子中由电子质子系统组成的能量场，严格说，应该只是数学表示上的一种方法和方式。这有不同的正和反面的证据。如电子的电场，它是真正的物理客观实在或事实上根本不存在物理场。例证：正负电子湮灭过程。从太阳到地球以光速传播也需要8分钟。如果电子电场分布按平方反比到无限远是真实的，无法在短时间内把其分布很远的场收回，并在实现湮灭的极短过程时间内完成。但实验上明确证实存在的电磁波表明光子的电磁场必须存在。这矛盾表明其电场分布可能客观地存在但确实是有限的，不是量子力学中无限远场的概念、描述和结论。电子如果有电场其分布界面事实上应该存在。

光子和基能。 作者为基能提出一个判断标准和准则：无序运动能量称为基能和有序运动能量则称为物质。具有不同有序性的基能组成不同的物质。光子是基能在连续动态转变模式运动中的一种有序存在形式。其电场和磁场都是基能有序运动形成的。在电磁场方面的特别有序化构成这里研究的光子。这应能建立起基能和光子以及在物理能量场和基能或物质之间的联系。例如，在粒子物理学中，据称夸克仅占强子质量的1%，其余由强子能量场组成。因此真空中的光子或电磁波是基能的有序运动的能量场。如果光子中的能量无序运动它将变回基能。反

之，在光子中的电磁场的分布和存在，不是任何已知物质的空间分布，正是基能存在的强力证据。

麦克斯韦方程组适用区域。 光子是检验麦克斯韦方程组在空间区域中的适用性及其正确性的一个很好实验场所，因为光子体积可涵盖从无线电波到 γ 射线的非常大的空间区域。麦克斯韦方程组可以很好地描述无线电波，即单个无线电波光子，由此可以继续测试沿着光子波长越来越短到趋近零或越长到数千公里、光年，或无限远。应该存在一个临界光子波长，低于该值麦克斯韦方程组不能工作。实验可发现和找到这个临界点。

可以研究单个光子在空间传播的动态过程。例如，解为平面波、球面波，波矢 K 为常量，在自由空间传播过程中光子的前端部分先移动和后端部分结束。通过与物体作用的反射波。真空中光子的能量随时间不变，即 $E=h\nu=const$ =光子的电场能+磁场能= $\epsilon_0 E^2/2+B^2/2\mu_0$ ，且与光子体积无关。光子电磁场的位相差，是否为 $\pi/2$ ，这应该精确检验。

光子周期数。 单个光子内应该包含多个电磁波周期。因为只含有一个周期，当光子传播通过节点时，它会损失接近其终点边界的光子结构信息。一个光子就是一个电磁波序列。包含在一个光子内的周期数是常数且其值可被测得。光子能量不同使其波长不同，但具有相同的光子周期数。提出的测量光子周期数的方法如实验 2 和图 2 所示。

机械地将一个光子切成两个光子。 用与图 2 和实验 2 类似的方法，可以机械地将一个光子切成两个光子。当一个光子正部分地穿过快速旋转的转轮的当时，转轮正好将其切割成两个光子。实验上可测试和证实其可行性。

图 1 光子圆柱形结构模型示意图。示例是光子周期数为 8 的电磁波构成的一个光子内部的电磁场转变结构。

光子间相互作用。 光子间的碰撞由其粒子性质是可能的。假设一个光子是能量最基本、最小的物质单元或形式。通过相互作用实现的形态改变模式，例如一个光子变为两个或更多光子、两个或多个光子变为或形成一个光子，都可以通过原子吸收和发射过程实现。具有较小体积的光子可以穿过一个具有较大体积的光子，可引起变化或不变，并且当其体积差异达到特定值时，即其临界体积差，两个光子间明显的相互作用效果将会被观测到和证实。长波长光子的表现性质像是波而很短波长光子表现得像粒子。例如，无线电具有很长波长表现得像波而 γ 射线具有很短波长表现得像粒子。

光子碰撞实验： 两束不同频率且相互垂直的激光，使其光子相互碰撞，测其光子频率有无改变，测不同方向或角度处有无光子。可用以检测光子碰撞的能量、动量守恒及其如何体现。该实验是基于光子具有粒子性，应该能表现出粒子碰撞特性的一面，并将展示光子的粒子碰撞特性包括相互作用强度等。

光子尺度测量实验

基于上述光子结构和特性的理论研究结果，拟先从实验上测量光子横向和纵向尺度大小的实验做起，开展对光子特性的深入研究。光子尺度测量实验装置如图 2 所示。

实验 1：测量一个光子传播方向的横向尺度的大小。从无线电波一直测到 γ 射线。形成一条光子横向尺度随波长或频率变化的曲线。检验所提出的光子尺度经验公式。并确定其中的系数。

图 2 光子横向尺度和传播方向长度测量实验装置的示意图。用双轮测量光子传播方向尺度的实验装置如图所示。多孔的双轮能快速转动以确定光子通过用时。双轮上的这些孔是光子通过的通道。对于光子横向尺度测量实验，需要移除装置中的双轮。

实验装置： 一个金属，如铝，制成的两个半球形成的可开合的球形空腔，也可以是方形或其它形状的。金属外壳起屏蔽作用。球形空腔内放置用于测量光子的光敏探测器和记录仪器等。单色光源安装在球形空腔外。球形空腔上开有通光小孔，供光子通过。单色光源和光敏探测器应该对相应波长的光子协调一致。测量短波长光子时，应在小孔上安放能通过相应波长的档板，例如不同的晶体片。见图 2。

实验时，改变通光孔径的大小，以便测量到使光子由不能通过到刚好能通过的转变点，则这时通光孔径的大小就应该是相应波长光子的尺度大小，可称为光子的宽度或直径或横向线度。直观物理推测形成的初步概念性结论表明，可以先合理的假设光子的结构为圆柱体或准圆柱体。圆柱的轴线方向为其传播方向。改变光源和探测器，则能测到所需要测量的光子尺度随波长变化的曲线。

测量机理： 光子能量越高，频率越高，波长越短，尺度就越小，能量大约与尺度成反比或逆变化。经验表明，穿透深度正比于光子能量，表明尺寸大者更难

以通过相同的介质间隙。 γ 射线能量最高，穿透最深，尺度最小。无线电波反之。

机制解释：为什么红外线对物质的穿透深度远低于 γ 射线。红外线对应光子的线度远大于 γ 射线光子的线度。尺度更大的光子更难穿过同样的物质间隙。

外推：中微子与物质的相互作用很弱，除其相互作用本身的特性外，也表明中微子的线度很小。应该比 γ 射线光子的线度要小得多。直观物理解，应该有：穿透力越强，穿透得越深，相互作用越弱，粒子的尺度越小。像筛子过滤的机理一样，尺度小于孔径的可通过，大的不可通过。因为物理原理是普适的。

近似公式正确性：光子和中微子实验结果能证实这里提出的近似公式的正确性。**近似公式：**中微子的线度 \times 中微子对物质的穿透深度 \approx 光子的线度 \times 光子对物质的穿透深度。光子实验结果能证实光子线度穿透深度标定律的存在性。

实验 2：测量一个光子沿其传播方向的长度。双轮实验用来测量光速。也可用来测量一个光子的长度。以光速运动的光子，在限定的时间内，前进的距离小于光子的长度时就无法通过双轮传播。据此应该能测量出光子的长度。至少对大光子，如无线电波，应该能测量出较为可信的实验结果。

光子传播方向长度的测量难度大。光速太快，光子的始终点难判定。随着光子的波长变短，实验难度会越来越大。

作者提出一个可表示光子长度的经验公式， $L = L_p \times d$ ，其中 L 代表光子传播方向的长度， d 为光子传播方向的横向直径， L_p 为系数。推测可能有 $2 < L_p < 10$ 。这可用双轮实验证实，见图 2。

基于图 2 所示的装置，可以测量光子的长度，从无线电波一直测到 γ 射线。形成一条光子传播方向尺度随波长或频率变化的曲线。检验所提出的光子长度经验公式。并确定其中的系数。

实验装置：双轮实验装置。在单色光源和光敏探测器之间安装双轮，双轮上开有均匀分布的通光孔，双轮间的间隙可调，双轮也可高速旋转。实验时，双轮转动并逐渐提高转速，测量出从光能通过至通光变弱至无光通过处。则光变弱处的双轮及其间隙对应的长度，可认为是相应波长光子的长度。

测量机理：光子以光速传播，在转动双轮限定的时间内，光传播的距离小于光子长度时，该长度的光子就无法通过双轮传播。远大于光子长度时，该长度的光子就能顺利通过双轮，且通过量较大并对应于测到的强光。等于光子的长度时，该长度的光子位置和始终点只有恰到好处才能通过双轮，即通过的光变弱处。

机制解释：单个光子内包含有几个振动周期。用其测得的长度除以波长即可给定光子周期数。一个光子内包含的振动周期个数是一个重要的物理量。也是光子结构研究中重要的物理参数。

外推：(1) 所有光子的振动周期个数都相等。光子周期数是一个物理常数。(2) 如果转轮旋转得足够快，当一个光子正部分地穿过快速旋转的转轮的当时，转轮能正好将其切割成两个光子。这可用测量通过的具有不同频率的光子或被切光子证实，并进行深入研究，例如在不同部位切割生成的两个新光子的关系和不同特性，光子频率改变，光子周期数改变等。

精确测量光速。 双轮精确测光速实验。用建好的装置，通过精确测量双轮的转速和间距，也能顺便精确测量光速。此即典型的双轮测光速实验。

实验 3：光子弯曲实验。 选择具有适当波长的光子，让光子通过直径比光子横向尺度稍大一点的管子，弯曲管子，使得当光子能通过管子时也是弯曲的。用不同形状的管子，例如直角形，能测试光子的形状是球形还是圆柱形的。如果光子能通过直角形管子，这能展示出光子的形状可能是球形或圆柱形和变形的，否则它会是刚性圆柱形的。这能检测光子的变形度。

光子弯曲实验的极限情况是弯曲一个光子成环，再假设能把其首尾相连构成一个闭环或环形光子，即一个闭环光子，则会发生什么？这种闭环光子将失去光速并获得静止质量，或不是这样。这将会是一个极大的实验挑战。

总结，提出一个可能的光子圆柱形结构模型及光子和基能间可能的关联。断定光子体积是有限的并有一个确定的表面和边界。每个光子都是单色的。可见光的光子尺度大约是氢原子的尺度。提出物质是基能的有序运动，基能的无序运动使其仍处于基能状态的观点。真空中的光子是基能的有序运动。如果光子中的能量无序的运动，它就会变回基能。光子中电磁场的分布和存在，不是任何已知物质的空间分布，是基能存在的确凿证据。提出实验 1、2 和 3 测量光子体积、光子横向尺度、光子传播方向长度、光子周期数、以及证明机械地把一个光子切成两个和弯曲一个光子的可能性。这些对光子特性的预言都可以通过提出的实验检验和证实。

Photon structure and characteristics

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Abstract

We first show a model for a single photon, a kind of photon column structure, and present photon characteristics, which can be confirmed experimentally. The light is electromagnetic waves with very short wavelength and composed of photons, which is confirmed experimentally, so a single photon is an electromagnetic wave. We found each photon is monochrome, the possible photon column structure and the possible relationship with Jineng. Jineng means elementary energy. The matter is the ordered motions of Jineng and the random motions of Jineng remains in the Jineng state. Photons or electromagnetic waves in vacuum are the ordered motions of Jineng, i.e. energy-field. If the energy in photons moved randomly it would become Jineng. The distribution and existence of electric and magnetic fields in photon, not any known matter distribution in space, is the strong evidence for the Jineng existence. Our results demonstrate how to understand and determine the photon volume, photon transverse-direction dimension, photon propagation-direction length, photon period number, and the feasibility to cut one photon into two photons mechanically and bending a photon, which can be tested experimentally. Otherwise, the suggested photon experiments and these photon dimension and feature experimental results will confirm the above facts, the photon boundary existence, and the relationship between the photon electric, magnetic field and the Jineng.

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Keywords: photon structure, photon transverse-direction dimension, photon propagation-direction length, photon period number, Jineng

One Sentence Summary: We first show a photon column structure model for a single photon and experiments to measure the photon volume, photon transverse-direction dimension, photon propagation-direction length, photon period number, and feasibility to cut one photon into two photons mechanically.

The light is electromagnetic waves with very short wavelength and composed of photons, which is confirmed experimentally. So a single photon is an electromagnetic wave.

There are many challenges for the photon researches which can be considered deeply. For example, a single photon, its shape, volume, and structures are what kind of? Is there the definite photon boundary? Forever, lossless electromagnetic field transform process is it and how to transform?

Here we present a photon structure model, see Fig. 1, based on the following physical analysis for the photon:

Photon boundary According to the principle of limit propagation velocity, namely less than or equal to the velocity of light, by photon emission and absorbing process, we could deduce photon is bounded. Because if its distribution is infinite, in the limited absorb or emission time, with limit velocity, it is impossible to return from infinite space distribution.

Photon integrality The boundary of photon, namely existing definite photon interface, can ensure the integrality of the photon. This meaning is, namely in the process of photon absorption, a wholly photon entirely absorbed, and that no any part of the photon remains as residual. This is confirmed by experiments, and in accord with the requirements and treating processes in quantum mechanics. The feature of photon integrality makes photons are stable and no decay. And the observed lights emitted from many light-years far away stars indicate photons propagating in the universe space are stable and no decay.

That would lead to the conclusion the electric field distribution of electron is bounded and has a definite interface in reality. Furthermore there would be an energy exchange process between the charged particles and the Jineng near the interface. Jineng means elementary energy.

Photon absorption and emission process Atoms absorb and emit visible lights, i.e. visible photons. Nuclei absorb and emit γ rays with different wavelength, i.e. γ photons. This process is a kind of transformation between the existing energy states, e.g. photons and the atomic electron-proton energy fields. So the assumption is reasonable: because the

FIG. 1: (Color online) The schematic diagram of the photon column structure model. It illustrates a photon is composed of electromagnetic waves with the photon period number of 8 here.

existing mode should be corresponding and compatible, the photon dimension should be close related to the dimension of its emission or absorption main-body. Hence, we can select the hydrogen atom dimension as the reference standard for the comparison or measurement of visible lights.

Photon monochromaticity A single photon is monochrome with a definite frequency only. The photon frequency emitted by the same atomic energy level may be different due to Doppler effect, but each photon is monochrome and this is confirmed by the spectrum analysis experiments. Based on this concept, the sun light spectrum, thought as continuous in physics, should not be continuous as that in mathematics and have the extreme tiny intervals between two neighboring photons due to formed by photons one by one.

Photon dimension Absorption and emission of visible photons are related to atoms and γ photons are related to nuclei. The dimension of atoms and nuclei is different so do visible and γ photons. Based on the reality above and the hydrogen atom spectrum as the reference standard, we present the photon dimension formula for visible photons. $L_\delta = \delta\nu_H/\nu$, where δ is the photon length factor, its value in the order of 1, unit \AA , ν_H is the hydrogen atom spectral frequency, ν is the visible photon frequency. The space shape of the photon is approximate column, the axis direction is its propagation direction, see Fig. 1, which can be confirmed and measured experimentally, see Fig. 2 and Experiments 1 and 2.

Photon structure Intuitionistic physical deductions form the primary conceptual conclusion indicates we may assume the photon structure and spatial distribution is a column

or quasi-column, see Fig. 1. The spatial energy or matter distribution within the photon volume and interface is the limited and closed electromagnetic wave. The dynamic electric and magnetic fields in phase are perpendicular as the plane electromagnetic wave. The axis direction of column is its propagating direction. Within the photon, the spatial distribution is a kind mode of ordered motion of Jineng or matter. The ordered Jineng forms photons is a reasonable assumption.

Light reflection process and Photon bending General point of view in academic community, a photon is not thought as point particle, namely it does not occupy space volume nor its size and length. When the finite length photon reflects, here it is not linear propagation. At the reflection point, a photon propagates by collision as particles or acting as waves, and its trace or line of propagation is an arcs of circles or a fold line. The key point is the photon size relative to the reflecting objects, e.g. visible photons are reflected by atoms by collision. Under the suitable condition a photon could be bent, see the possible photon bending Experiment 3.

Field concept Field, e.g. electron electric fields or the energy field in atoms formed by the electron-proton system, exactly speaking, should exist objectively or only be one way and mode of mathematical representation. There are different positive and negative evidences. For example, the electric field of electron, it is the genuine physics objective actuality or there is no physical field actually. Evidence illustration: positive-negative electron annihilation process. It needs 8 minutes from the sun to the earth in velocity of light as well. If the electron electric field distribution according to the square inverse proportion to infinite distance is true, it has no means of withdrawal the field distribution far away in such a short time, within the extremely short executing annihilation process, to perform. But the electromagnetic waves confirmed experimentally clearly indicate the photon electric and magnetic fields must exist. This contradiction indicates the distribution of electric field exists objectively but is limited indeed, not infinite as the description in quantum mechanics. The distribution boundary and interface of electron electric field should exist actually.

Photon and Jineng We suggest a judgement standard and criteria for Jineng: the random energy-fields are referred to as Jineng and the ordered energy-fields then are referred to as the physical fields or matter. Energy-fields with different in-order forms different matter. The photon is a kind of ordered existing form of Jineng under continuously dynamic transform mode movement. Both the electric field and magnetic field all are formed with

Jineng in ordered motion. The special order in electromagnetic field forms the photon, which is investigated here. This could build up the relationship between Jineng and photons, and between the physical energy-fields and the Jineng or matter too. For example, in particle physics, quarks only occupy hadron mass of 1%, the rest is composed of the energy-field of hadron. Hence photons or electromagnetic waves in vacuum are the ordered motions of Jineng, i.e. energy-field. If the energy in photons moved randomly it would become Jineng. Contrarily, the distribution and existence of electric and magnetic fields in photon, not any known matter distribution in space, is the strong evidence for the Jineng existence.

Maxwell equations working well region The photon is a very good experimental ground to test the correctness in the space region where Maxwell equations can work well because the photon volume can cover a very large space range from radio wave to γ ray. Maxwell equations can describe radio waves well, i.e. a single radio wave photon, and so we can continue to test it along with the shorter or longer photon wavelength approaching to zero or to thousands kilometers, light-years, or infinite. There should be a critical photon wavelength under which Maxwell equations can not work. This critical point can be found experimentally.

We can investigate the dynamical process of a single photon propagation in space. For example, the plane wave or spherical wave solutions, constant wave vector \mathbf{K} , initial part moving ahead and final part ending of photons in the free propagation process. Reflecting wave is by the interacting with objects. The photon energy is constant with time in vacuum, i.e. $E = h\nu = \text{constant} = \text{electric field energy of photon} + \text{magnetic field energy of photon} = \varepsilon E^2/2 + B^2/(2\mu)$, which is no relationship of the photon volume. The phase difference of electromagnetic field of photon should be tested exactly.

Photon period number There should be many electromagnetic wave periods included within a single photon. Because of only one period when a photon propagates to pass the node it would loss the photon structure information near its endpoint boundary. One photon is a serial of electromagnetic wave. The period number included in a photon is constant and the value of period number can be measured. Different photon energy makes its wavelength different, but with the same photon period number. The suggested method to measure the photon period number is shown in Experiment 2 and Fig. 2.

Mechanically cut one photon into two photons By the similar method shown in Fig. 2 and Experiment 2, one can cut one photon into two photons mechanically. When the

photon partly passes through the fast rotating wheel, the wheel just cuts the photon into two photons at the same time. The feasibility can be tested and confirmed experimentally.

Interaction among photons The photon collisions by its particle property would be possible. We assume a photon is the most basic, lowest form or unit of energy. The interacting formations, e.g. a photon becomes two or more photons, two or more photons become or form a photon, can be realized by the atomic absorption and emission process. A photon with less volume can penetrate a photon with bigger volume to cause change or not, and when the volume difference reaches the value, i.e. the critical volume difference, the obviously interacting effects of two photons would be observed and confirmed. The behave properties of long wave length photons are shown wave-like and very short wave length photons are shown particle-like. For example, radio with very long wave length behaves like wave and γ ray with very short wave length behaves like particles.

Photon collision experiment: two beam lasers with different frequency and perpendicular, collide with each other. One can measure if the photon frequency changes, if there are photons in different angle or direction. The energy and momentum conservation could be tested and the mode how to realize and present. This experiment is based on the photon with particle property, should put out the side of particle collision feature, and would illustrate the particle collision feature of photons.

Photon dimension measurement experiments

Based on the above theoretical investigation results of the photon structure and characteristics, we can first perform the experiment to measure the photon transverse-direction and longitudinal-direction dimension, carry on the photon characteristic in-depth research. The photon dimension measurement experiment devices are shown in Fig. 2.

Experiment 1 Measure the photon transverse-direction dimension of propagation direction. From radio wave until to γ ray, one can form the curve of the photon transverse-direction dimension as a function of wavelength or frequency, and verify the empirical formula suggested for the photon dimension and determine the coefficients.

Experimental apparatus: One metal, for instance aluminium, spherical cavity made-up two semi-spheres can be open or close, may be squareness or other shape. The metal cavity works on shielding effect. The light-sensitive detector to measure the photons and the recording instruments etc are put within the spherical cavity. The monochromatic source fits on the spherical cavity out. There is a pinhole on the spherical cavity for photons

FIG. 2: Photon transverse-direction dimension and propagation-direction length measurement experiment. The schematic diagram of the experimental apparatus to measure the photon propagating direction dimension with the double wheels. The double wheels with many holes can rotate very fast to determine the photon pass-time and the holes are for photons through. For the photon transverse-direction dimension measurement experiment, the double wheel parts are moved away.

passing through. The monochromatic source and light-sensitive detector should tune match for the same wavelength photon. When one measures the short wavelength photons, one should put the board, for instance different crystal wafer, on the pinhole let the photon with corresponding wavelength through. See Fig. 2.

When experiment, one changes the size of transmission aperture, so that one can measure the transition point to make the photons from impassability to just pervious over, then the size of transmission aperture can be supposed to be the corresponding wavelength photon dimension, it can be referred to as the photon transverse-direction dimension or photon width. By the above physical deductions to form the primary conceptual conclusion, we can reasonably assume the photon structure is column or quasi-column. The axial direction of column is its propagation direction. Changing the light source and detector, then one can measure the curve of photon transverse-direction dimension as a function of wavelength.

Measure mechanism: The higher of the photon energy the higher of its frequency, and the less of its dimension. Photon energy is about inverse proportion to its dimension. Experimental results indicate the depth of penetration is directly proportional to the photon energy, which indicates the larger of its size is the much more difficult to pass through the same medium gaps. The γ ray energy is the highest, it can penetrate the deepest, its dimension is the least, and radio waves on the contrary.

Interpret mechanism: The physical reason why infrared rays penetrate the material depth is far less than γ rays is that the dimension of infrared ray photons is far larger than the dimension of γ ray photons, and it is much more difficult to penetrate the same material gaps for the bigger photons.

Extrapolate: The interaction of neutrinos with matter is very weak, except its interaction characteristic, which as well indicates the neutrino dimension is very tiny. It should be much less than the dimension of γ ray photons. Intuitionistic physics understanding, there should be: the stronger the penetrating power the deeper the penetration, and the weaker the interaction is, the less the particle dimension is. Similar to the mechanism of sifter filtration, the dimension is less than the aperture can pass through, the larger cannot pass through, since the physics principles are universal.

Approximate formula correctness: The photon and neutrino experimental results can confirm the correctness of this approximate formula presented here. The neutrino dimension \times the neutrino material penetration depth = the photon dimension \times the photon material penetration depth. And the photon experimental results can confirm the existence of the photon dimension-penetration depth scaling law.

Experiment 2 Measure the photon length along its propagation direction. The double wheel experiment is used to measure velocity of light. It can be used to measure the length of a single photon too. Photons move in velocity of light, within the limitative time, the moved distance is less than the photon length just have no means of passing through the double wheels to propagate. Hereby this experiment could measure out the photon length. At least for large photons, for instance radio waves, it should measure out more creditable experimental results.

It is difficult to measure the photon length in the photon propagation direction. Velocity of light is too fast, it is very difficult to judge the first and last point of photons. Along with the photon wavelength becoming shorter, the difficult degree of experiment would be more and more.

We can present the empirical formula of photon length as, $L = Lp \times D$, here L represents the photon length of its propagation direction, D the transverse-direction width of photon propagation direction, Lp coefficient. We think there might be $2 < Lp < 10$. This can be confirmed by the double wheel experiment, see Fig. 2.

Based on the device shown in Fig. 2, one can measure the photon length, from radio

wave until γ ray, form the curve of photon propagation direction dimension as a function of wavelength and frequency, and verify the empirical formula suggested above for the photon length and determine the coefficients.

Experimental apparatus: Double wheel experiment. The double wheels are fixed between the monochromatic source and the light-sensitive detector. There are evenly distributed holes on the double wheels for photons through. The gap between the double wheels can be adjusted and the wheels can rotate at high speed. When experiment begins, the double wheels rotate and gradually increase the rotational speed, one measures the points from the light can pass through them, to the light becomes weak, and to no light passes through them. Then the length of double wheels and their gap corresponding the light becoming weak, can be considered as the photon length of corresponding wavelength.

Measure mechanism: Photons move in velocity of light, within the rotating double wheels limitative time, the light propagating distance is less than the photon length which just has no means of passing through the double wheels to propagate. When the light propagating distance is far larger than the photon length, these photons can easily pass through the double wheels, and the photon number passed is much larger corresponding the strong light detected. The distance is equal to the photon length, limited by the photon position and the first and last point of photon column, only the photon to a turn can pass through the double wheels, namely where the passed light becomes weak.

Interpret mechanism: There are how many vibration periods within a single photon. With its measured length divided by its wavelength we can set the photon period number. The vibration period number included within one photon is an important physical quantity and an important physical parameter in the photon structure research.

Extrapolate: (1) The vibration period number of all photons is equal. The photon period number is a physical constant. (2) If the wheel rotates fast enough it could cut one photon into two photons when the photon just partly passes through it. This experiment would be possible and feasible at least for the bigger photon. One can measure the resultant photons or cut photons with different frequency to confirm, and deeply investigate further, e.g. the relationship and different feature of two new photons produced by cutting at different position, photon frequency change, photon period number change, etc.

Accurately measure velocity of light Double wheels accurately measure velocity of light experiment. One can accurately measure the rotation speed of double wheels and the

gap as well so one can accurately measure the velocity of light with the built devices by the way. This is the typical double wheel experiment to measure the velocity of light.

Experiment 3 Photon bending experiment. To select photons with suitable wave length, let photons pass through a tube which diameter is a little larger than the photon transverse-direction dimension. The tube is bended so the photons are bended when they can pass through. This could test the photon shape is spherical or columnar by different tube shapes, e.g. a right angle. If the photons can pass the right angle tube this could demonstrate the photon shape would be spherical or columnar and deformable, otherwise it would be columnar and rigid. This can test the photon deformability. The limit of photon bending experiment is to bend a photon and connect the head and tail of the photon to form a loop or circle photon, i.e. a loop-photon, then what will happen? The loop-photon loses the velocity of light and obtains the rest mass or not. This should be a great experimental challenge.

In summary, we suggest a possible photon column structure model and the possible relationship between photons and the Jineng or matter. We conclude that the photon volume is limited and has a definite surface and boundary. Each photon is monochrome. The photon dimension of visible light is about the hydrogen atom size. The matter is the ordered motions of Jineng and the random motions of Jineng remains in the Jineng state is suggested. Photons in vacuum are the ordered motions of Jineng. If the energy in photons moved randomly it would become Jineng. The distribution and existence of electric and magnetic fields in photon, not any known matter distribution in space, would be the strong evidence for the Jineng existence. We suggest experiments 1, 2 and 3 to measure the photon volume, photon transverse-direction dimension, photon propagation-direction length, photon period number, and prove the feasibility to cut one photon into two photons mechanically and bending a photon. Our predictions on photon characteristics can be tested and confirmed experimentally.